

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15011822

Principals Orientation And Induction Practices As Predictors Of Teacher Productivity In Public Senior Secondary Schools In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This examined the relationship between Principals' orientation and induction practices and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study was guided by eight objectives with corresponding research questions and null hypotheses. The study adopted a correlational research design. Population of this study consisted of all three hundred and eleven (311) public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. 380 teachers are representing all of the schools. They were selected using purposive and stratified random sampling techniques. The instruments titled: 'Principals' Orientation and Induction Practices Assessment Scale' and 'Teacher Productivity Assessment Scale' were adopted. The instruments were validated by three experts from Educational management and Measurement and Evaluation, University of Port Harcourt. Research questions was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Formula (r). The z ratio was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The results of the findings revealed that the productivity of teachers' job is significantly enhanced when principals implement a range of assimilation practices for teaching staff. These practices include providing orientation programmes for new teaching staff, and conducting structured induction programmes. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that school management should ensure that teachers are properly oriented on the proper use of education tools to determine the extent to which the objectives of secondary education are being achieved.

Keywords: Principals', teaching staff, orientation and induction practices, teacher productivity.

INTRODUCTION

The socio-economic development of any given country is dependent on the quality of education provided to its citizens. Education, be it formal, informal, or non-formal has always served as an avenue through which values, skills, attitudes, and belief systems required for continued existence of the society, as well as mankind are acquired, sustained, modified, and eventually passed on from one generation to another. Education is an instrument for developing human intellect, technical skills, character and effective citizenship for self-reliance and national development. A simple way of appreciating education is that it is a tool or a necessary weapon that is needed by every human being and society in other to navigate our complex world. Education in essence is the most effective instrument for academic progress, social survival, political mobilization, and effective national development of a country. Education is also the key to the development of an individual for the acquisition of competent skills and knowledge necessary important for personal and national development. Put differently, it is the transmission of what is desirable to individuals to make them knowledgeable and contributing members of the society.

Education in Nigeria is an instrument of excellence for effective national development (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). The National Policy on Education points out that, the main objectives of education at all levels in Nigeria is to raise the quality of education in order to make the products of the system very useful to the society and to maintain education as one of the prime engines for development and supply of manpower. For a nation to rise to an enviable height and be able to compete globally carrying the League of Nations, such nation must endeavor that high quality is attained and sustained in her educational system because education is an effective tool for meaningful development to take place. The level to which the above expectation of the government is achieved depends hugely on the quality of education provided to her citizens.

Secondary school teachers and staff assimilation practice

The principal of a secondary school is the planner, director, controller, coordinator, organizer, adviser, and problems-solver who identifies, set goals and objectives of the school, analyses tasks and shares responsibilities to the members of staff according to their areas of specialization and expertise. The principal being the chief Executive of the school is charged with the budgeting, staffing, motivating, directing and evaluating of activities in the secondary institution. Ogbonnaya (2013) stresses that, administrative process can be regarded as the sum total of the various processes of planning, organizing, stimulating, coordinating, staffing, budgeting, communicating and evaluating, which aid administrators in the utilization of resources in the achievement of organizational goals. A school that thrives as expected is built on solid planning and flawless execution of those plans. The principal holds a critical role in this journey, by expertly leading and managing the members of staff. A principals' strong ethical and moral values help to ensure that the school policies and practices are fair, just and equitable for all students and staff. While principals may communicate their vision and establish the culture of the school, it is ultimately the responsibility of the teachers to adhere to this and work to achieve the desired results. In order to support their teachers, the principals should be able to monitor their performance and identify areas where they can improve. Additionally, a principal should provide teachers with ample training opportunities to help them grow professionally and develop skills that can serve and improve 21st century students.

Proper staff assimilation practice is the surest, strongest and fastest wheel of movement in the achievement of the expected productivity in any organizational set-up. According to Ogbonnaya (2013), when the principal of a secondary school engages the academic institution and its teaching staff in the appropriate assimilation practices, especially from the on-set of their employment, their productivity is likely to be high, such principals' assimilation practices as induction programmes, orientation programmes, mentoring practices, supervision practices will start them well in the job and be a boost to teachers' productivity. As these needful assimilation practices are carried out by the principals for their teaching staff, they can assure-ably predict that their teachers will deliver appropriately and professionally in the classroom teaching, which will reflect on the academic performances of their students in the school, both on internal and external examinations. The principals can also use the proper assimilation practices carried out as standard to assure that every student taught by the teachers shall excel anywhere they find themselves nationally and internationally, as their performances and contributions will be enviable ones in the society.

Principals' teaching staff orientation practice and teacher productivity

Orientation is the introduction phase in the process of assimilating teachers into a school. This is where new teachers are welcomed and introduced into the system. It is aimed at educating them about the goals and responsibilities of the position they have been given. This orientation is usually done on the first day of work, where they are given a warm welcome in the form of an introduction to the school authorities and co-workers. Orientation can be viewed as a special kind of training designed to help new employees to learn about their task, to be introduced to their co-workers and to settle in their work situation-a vital ingredient of internal corporate communication (Benneth, 2011). Employee orientation can be broadly defined as the familiarization with, and adaptation to, a new work environment. It refers to a process by which a new employee is introduced to the organization, to the work group, and to do the job. Traditionally, organizations approach orientation by describing to the new employee the organization's history, structure, fringe benefits, rules and regulations.

Most times, a welcome party is also provided for depending on the school. Ingram (2009) posits that orientation means the direction in which something points. It is seen by some as the process of getting the newly employed

teachers pointed to the right direction in order to meet the aim and objectives of the school. It is planned so as to acquaint the new teacher with the demands of his work setting. This orientation consists of the school policies and guidelines, mission statements, dress codes, ethics, working hours, parents' policies, office equipment, stationeries, instructional materials, internet and e-mail use and so on. Principals orientation practice aids newly employed teachers to become comfortable in their new place of work. It is also the process of integrating the new teachers into the visions and culture of the school. Orientation, aside the fact that procedural activities and safety awareness are addressed, often takes place as an intensive full day training session. Uche (2008) is of the opinion that principals should provide orientation exercise for their teachers, adding that it is in such exercise that teachers gain insights into the mode of conduct of the school, gathers information which will enable him/her know the sort of issues or questions to be asked. She further states that orientation raises the enthusiasm of the new teacher.

Principals orientation practice is designed to welcome the new teachers into their new work place. This exercise is aimed for new teachers to settle down on their new jobs easily without difficulties. The practice is used to create a friendly working environment between new and old teachers. Orientation aims at enhancing comfort in the new teacher by reducing any anxiety or unresolved negative emotions because new teachers tend to exhibit tendencies of fear and reluctance to engage fully in their duties during their first days at work. Orientation practice is very necessary to lay a foundation for the new employees, mainly to provide them with concise information about how things are done in the school as to make them more comfortable in the teaching profession.

Orientation can be viewed as a special kind of training designed to help new employees to learn about their task, to be introduced to their co-workers and to settle in their work situation-a vital ingredient of internal corporate communication (Benneth, 2011). Employee orientation can be broadly defined as the familiarization with, and adaptation to, a new work environment. It refers to a process by which a new employee is introduced to the organization, to the work group, and to do the job. Traditionally, organizations approach orientation by describing to the new employee the organization's history, structure, fringe benefits, rules and regulations. A classroom is a space provided in a school where students gather and the teacher meets them for lectures. Classroom is a room set aside and specifically designed and furnish for the purpose of teaching and learning (Agabi, 2013). For classroom to be useful for the purpose it was meant to serve, it has to be organized and maintain. This brings about the concept of classroom management. Classroom management refers to the sum total plan of actions taken by the teacher in the classroom to bring about conducive classroom environment that supports teaching and learning leading to success and achievement. Wali, (2013) defined classroom management as the process and strategies an educator uses to maintain a classroom environment that is conducive to students learning and success. Teachers in the classroom are the managers of the classroom activities. He or she is concerned with maintaining order, regulating the sequence of events and directing his/her own attention towards achieving educational goals. The success of any educational system depends largely on the effectiveness of classroom management. Classroom management techniques have been divided into two major components, behavioural management and instructional management (Martin & Sass, 2010).

Finally, a good orientation practice can develop impression on the school, just like a first impression of an individual helps to form a good relationship so also an impression of the school, creates a good relationship between the staff and the new teachers, thereby making them adjust better. Furthermore, effective orientation practice can have a lasting effect on absenteeism and turnover, and also enhance the performance of the new teachers because the rate at which they would have made mistake will be reduced.

Principals' Teaching Staff Induction Practice and Teacher Productivity

The term 'induction' has considerable degree of divergent definitions and applications in both educational and institutional contexts. Induction is a form of training given to a new staff so as to disclose the expected standard programme of behaviour, rules and regulation of the organization to him/her. It is a way of making the new staff adjust or acclimatize to their new environment. Kessels (2010) defined induction programme as a process of introducing beginner teachers into their new post and familiarizing their roles with official responsibilities as teachers, alongside with associated obligations as members of the school community. Furthermore, induction has also been defined as the process by which newly employed teachers are incorporated and symphonized into

school community, so that they will become effective members of the school community (Nghaamwa, 2017). Onuoha (2007) sees induction as a systematic approach of introducing new teachers to the organization and to their tasks, superiors and work groups. Induction is a practice that provide sustained assistance to beginning teachers in their first year in the hope that such support will create the first of many magical years. Induction can be seen as the process of receiving and welcoming new teachers into the school system, helping them settle down and get to work by dishing out basic information about the organization to them so as to fast track their productivity (Armstrong, 2003). The cardinal objective of induction is to provide enough support for newly employed teachers to navigate through the challenges that beset beginner teachers, and also to help them to move forward in their career as a teacher (Hendrik, 2016). Although induction programme may take place during probation period or before the new teacher is assigned duties, its ultimate goal is to impart, integrate the beginner teacher into the school community and to school them on the behaviour that support effective teaching and learning (Grimble, 2017). One important aspect of training exercise which organizations should participate in with the aim of increasing productivity and motivation of new teachers while improving the organization's culture is induction. It is an avenue to clear any doubts in the minds of new teachers about their new job and administrators.

Induction practice is a training session that assists the new teachers to understand clearly what is expected of them by the school. This satisfies the teachers' need of acceptance and also motivate them to work hard. It helps the new employee to understand the educational resources available in the school and be able to effectively make use of them. In an induction exercise, the school and new teachers develop a relationship that is necessary in benchmarking standards that are to be observed and behaviours to be learned. These are all part of the school's culture, and the idea is that this process is clinical in nature. Research has shown that teachers retention is improved when they participate on induction programmes at the beginning of their job, therefore, schools should have well-structured induction programmes in place as it will maximize productivity. Induction programme helps to explain to new comers the way things are done in a particular organization so that misappropriations are reduced even if all cannot be eliminated (Armstrong, 2003).

Wrong as cited by Nghaamwa, (2017) highlighted that the pivotal role of school and teacher is not only centered on helping students achieve academically, but teaching students how to succeed in life. The scholar emphasized that the school can only achieve this goal if the most contributing factor in educational process (the teacher) is properly educated on the pedagogical skills and enabling behavioural facilities that aid teaching and learning. Nakpodia (2008) remarked that the effectiveness of induction exercise predicts the degree of challenges a novice teacher is likely to encounter during probation, as well as the likelihood of remaining in teaching profession (as cited by Nghaamwa, 2017). This is because if the induction programme fails to allay the fears and doubts about succeeding as a teacher, provide succor to the new teacher and sense of belonging, the novice teacher will with time become disconnected from the school community, which will pave way for dissatisfaction and eventual withdrawal from the school. Mlindazwe (2010) acknowledged that teachers normally face varying degrees of fears during their first few years of employment in the profession, noting that induction programmes must be designed to address those jitters. As the new teacher travails in attempt to balance apply learnt contradictory theories in a pragmatic and unfamiliar environment classroom setting, she is faced with strain and burnout may ensue and even deteriorate into discontentment and attrition. Attrition in this context is the number of newly employed teachers that exit teaching profession before the sixth year of their employment (Mingo, 2012). Owens (2015) reported that 44% of newly employed teachers do not stay beyond five years in teaching profession due to inadequacies of administrative support, poor working environment and lack of quality instructional resources as well as the resultant burnout arising from the above factors. The findings of Owens are supported by observations of Nghaamwa (2017) who opined that unfavourable working environment causes novice teachers to undergo unnecessary stress that not only affects their confidence and self-worth, but also their professional identity and growth. Thus, it is imperative that newly employed teachers are not exposed to impressions that will cast skepticism about their career choices in education. In this regard Lunenburg (2011) urges that strong and institutionalize support programmes like induction, should be provided for the newly employed teachers; a platform whereby they are educated on how to do their jobs better, by actual guidance on how to swim rather than left to sink. This is because learning by trial and error without guidance of

more knowledgeable teachers is not only wasteful and morale dampening, but also costly to the school that employed the new teacher.

Statement of the problem

Teacher productivity in Rivers State is an important issue of discourse, especially when examining the level of students' academic and moral performances. It is believed that newly recruited teachers in any school system need to be adequately assimilated into the school system in order to enhance their productivity. Teachers assimilation if properly implemented and followed up by school principals on newly recruited teachers can make the new teachers acclimatize faster and fit in better into their new job and environment, as well as be able to give their best with ease. With this in mind, it becomes a key responsibility to make sure that everything is possibly done to make sure new teachers go through all the needed assimilation programmes such as induction, supervision, mentoring, training, orientation, and talent management programmes. Unfortunately, the state of things now appears to be the direct opposite of what is expected. We have new teachers who most times have little or no background knowledge of the teaching sector being allowed to go into the profession and do whatever they like, without the school principals also bothered about what the teachers have to offer. Rather, we find principals who are less concerned about happenings and are unconcerned about discharging expected duties of bringing new teachers up to expected speed and knowledge. But instead, we see principals who are relaxed and feel it's a waste of time and resources for new teachers to go through the assimilation programmes. Some of them go as far as pocketing the funds meant for these various programmes, some of them don't see it as important at all.

On the other hand, there are school principals who make prevalent efforts in making sure that new teachers are properly assimilated, but most times the teachers take with levity some of the various programmes they undergo, which is the reason for the poor students' performance academically and otherwise. With the above, the researcher becomes bothered whether assimilation of new teachers cannot lead to productivity. Hence the need to determine the relationship between orientation and induction and teacher productivity.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study examined the relationship between Principals' orientation and induction practices and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Specifically, the objectives were to:

1. examine the prediction of principals' orientation practices on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. determine the prediction of principals' induction practices on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools' in Rivers state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in the study:

1. What is the prediction of principals' orientation practices on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. What is the prediction of principals' induction practices on teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant prediction of principals' orientation practices on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant prediction of principals' induction practices on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The correlational research design was used for this study. The correlational design was considered appropriate because the study seeks to examine the magnitude of the relationship that exists between Principals' teaching staff assimilation practices and teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The population of this study consisted of all three hundred and eleven (311) public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

(Planning, Research and Statistics Department, RSSSSB, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, 2024). There are 6,174 teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The total sample size for the study was 380 teachers, which comprised both male and female. This sample size was arrived at after applying the Taro Yamane minimum sample size determination formula. These respondents were distributed among 195 female and 185 male teachers in selected public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. They were selected using purposive and stratified random sampling techniques. Two self-developed instruments were used as the medium through which data were obtained for this research. The instruments are titled: ‘Principals’ Orientation and Induction Practices Assessment Scale’ (PIOPAS), and ‘Teacher Productivity Assessment Scale’ (TPAS). The instruments used for this study were subjected to content and face validity. The validation was done by three experts, from the department of Educational Management, as well as from Measurement and Evaluation, under the Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling, who examined and made corrections on the instruments, their suggestions were used as guide in preparing the final draft of the instruments. The reliability of the two instruments were determined by the use of the Cronbach Alpha formula. The researcher administered 20 copies of the instruments to 20 respondents (teachers) outside the drawn respondents’ area, the data was analyzed using SPSS version 27.0.1 to determine the reliability coefficients of the 2 clusters of the first instrument and the second instrument. Three hundred and eighty (380) copies of the instruments were administered by the researcher and two research assistants. Respondents were given 2 hours to respond to the instruments. On retrieval, 375 were retrieved, which represented 99 percent of the respondents. In the process of coding, 3 were discarded, leaving a total of 372. This 372 represent the 98 percent of the total number administered and 99 percent of the total number retrieved. The responses from the respondents were made available for analysis. Research questions were answered using Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, while z ratio was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level using SPSS version 27.0.1 analysis tool.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the prediction of principals’ orientation practices on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Hypothesis (Ho₁): There is no significant prediction of principals’ teaching staff orientation practices on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4.1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Analysis Showing the Prediction of Principals’ Orientation Practices on Teacher Productivity in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Variables	N	df	R	P (Sig.)	Decision
Teaching Staff Orientation Practices	372	370	0.612	0.000	Reject Ho ₁ (Significant)
Teacher Productivity	372				P <0.05

Decision Rule: 0.00 – 0.25 = Very Weak, 0.26 – 0.50 = Weak, 0.51 – 0.75 = Strong, 0.71 – 1.00 = Very Strong

The data on Table 4.1 indicates a strong correlation coefficient, 'r' of 0.612, suggesting a strong prediction of the impact of principals' teaching staff orientation practices on teacher productivity. Based on the finding, the researcher established that there is a strong prediction of principals' teaching staff orientation practices on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Furthermore, the hypothesis testing from Table 4.1 demonstrates that, the correlation coefficient of 0.612 is statistically significant with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the critical value of 0.05. As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating a significant prediction of principals' teaching staff orientation practices on teacher productivity. Based on the above observation, the researcher established that there is a significant

prediction of principals' teaching staff orientation practices on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Research Question 2: *What is the prediction of principals' induction practices on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Hypothesis (Ho₂): There is no significant prediction of principals' teaching staff induction practices on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4.2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Showing the Prediction of Principals Induction Practices on Teacher Productivity in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Variables	N	df	R	P (Sig.)	Decision
Teaching Staff Induction Practices	372	370	0.693	0.000	Reject Ho ₂ (Not Significant)
Teacher Productivity	372				P < 0.05

Decision Rule: 0.00 – 0.25 = Very Weak, 0.26 – 0.50 = Weak, 0.51 – 0.75 = Strong, 0.71 – 1.00 = Very Strong

The data on Table 4.2 indicates a strong correlation coefficient, denoted as 'r', of 0.693. This suggests a strong prediction of principals' induction practices on teachers' productivity. Based on the finding, the researcher established that there is a strong prediction of principals' induction practices on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Furthermore, the results from Table 4.2 also demonstrated that, the correlation coefficient of 0.693 is statistically significant with a probability value (P) of less than 0.05 (P < 0.05). This indicates that the null hypothesis can be rejected. In essence, the data suggests a significant prediction of principals' induction practices on teachers' productivity. Based on the above observation, the researcher established that there is a significant prediction of principals' induction practices on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS/IMPLICATION

Principals' Orientation Practices on Teacher Productivity in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

The first finding of the research established that there is a strong prediction of principals' orientation practices on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Also, the researcher established that there is a significant prediction of principals' teaching staff orientation practices on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State. This is in line with the finding of Ingram (2009), which posits that, orientation is the direction in which something points. It is seen by some as the process of getting the newly employed teachers pointed to the right direction in order to meet the aim and objectives of the school. It is planned so as to acquaint the new teacher with the demands of his work setting. This orientation consists of the school policies and guidelines, mission statements, dress codes, ethics, working hours, parents' policies, office equipment, stationeries, instructional materials, internet and e-mail use and so on. Uche (2008) is of the opinion that principals should provide orientation exercise for their teachers, adding that it is in such exercise that teachers gain insights into the mode of conduct of the school, gathers information which will enable him/her know the sort of issues or questions to be asked. She further states that orientation raises the enthusiasm of the new teacher.

Orientation aims at enhancing comfort in the new teacher by reducing any anxiety or unresolved negative emotions because new teachers tend to exhibit tendencies of fear and reluctance to engage fully in their duties during their first days at work. Orientation practice is very necessary to lay a foundation for the new employees, mainly to provide them with concise information about how things are done in the school as to make them more comfortable in the teaching profession.

Principals' Induction Practices on Teacher Productivity in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

The second finding of the research established that there is a strong prediction of principals' induction practices on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Similarly, the research established that there is a strong prediction of principals' induction practices on teachers' productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The finding aligns with Armstrong (2003) who sees induction as a programme that provides sustained assistance to beginning teachers in their first year in the hope that such support will create the first of many magical years. He further maintains that one aspect of exercise, organizations should participate in with an aim of increasing productivity and motivation of new teacher while improving the schools culture is induction. Also, Kessels (2010) in agreement with the above sees induction programme as a process of introducing beginner teachers into their new post and familiarizing their roles with official responsibilities as teachers, alongside with associated obligations as members of the school community. Furthermore, induction has also been defined as the process by which newly employed teachers are incorporated and symphonized into school community, so that they will become effective members of the school community. Research has shown that some new teachers leave the teaching profession within their first 3-5 years due to different reasons, among which is lack of induction. An effective induction practice enhances the commitment performance and productivity of the new employees because the rate at which they would have made such mistakes will be reduced.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research findings, it is concluded that the productivity of teachers is significantly enhanced when principals implement a range of orientation and induction practices for teaching staff. These practices include providing comprehensive orientation programmes for new teaching staff to familiarize them with the school's culture and policies, conducting structured induction programmes to help new teachers integrate into the school community. It is evident that these multifaceted practices play a crucial role in nurturing and amplifying teachers' creative abilities within their respective subject areas when implemented with care and attention to individual needs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The school management should continually ensure that teachers are properly oriented on the proper use of education tools to determine the extent to which the objectives of secondary education are being achieved.
2. The principals should continuously establish structured induction programmes for newly recruited teachers to acquaint them with the fundamental operations of the school. Principals should prioritize exploring potential strategies for furnishing staff offices to enhance their suitability for work. This will contribute to cultivating a positive and conducive environment for teachers to engage in tasks such as lesson planning, assessing students' work, and other essential school responsibilities.

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